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Nigeria's Water Crisis And The Challenge Of Meeting The Sustainable Development Goals.

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ABSTRACT

Water is a very important natural resource and it's central in the achievement of sustainable development. Evidence from the literature suggests that access to water across Nigeria is still very low. The country is facing a water scarcity problem that will metamorphose into a water crisis if concerted efforts are not put in place to check the situation. Some of the forces driving Nigeria towards a water crisis include climate change, population growth, increased water demand, decaying water infrastructure, overuse of water etc. This paper examines the implication of a water crisis on the drive to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Nigeria. Since almost all the SDGs have a form of linkage with water, the paper concludes that real achievement of the SDGs will depend on willingness of the Government and the people to improve water supply. The paper suggests sustainable water management practices that will help to avert the looming water crisis in Nigeria.

Keywords: Water crisis, Water scarcity, Sustainable Development Goals, Water Resource Management

INTRODUCTION

“Water has the power to enhance life; it also has the power to destroy it.”

Ellen Johnson Sirleaf, President of Liberia, Goodwill Ambassador for Water, Sanitation and Hygiene in Africa - statement made as part of an interview marking the World Water Day, 2013.

The epigraph above highlights the importance of water and its centrality in the achievement of sustainable development. All spheres of life or human endeavour- from food, energy, health, industry and biodiversity depend on the availability of water which is unfortunately in short supply.

Almost three quarters of the Earth's surface is covered in water, but less than 3% of this resource is actually freshwater, of which maybe only 1% is readily accessible (World Wide Fund for Nature, 2017). As the global demand for water increases, fresh water is becoming even scarcer. The Edmonton Journal of Canada (2010) has aptly summarized the tragedy of global water scarcity: “The world is running out of water. Humans are polluting, depleting, and diverting its finite freshwater supplies so quickly, we are creating massive new deserts and generating global warming from below.” It is projected that by 2025, 1.8 billion people will be living in countries or regions with absolute water scarcity, and two-thirds of the world's population could be living under water stressed conditions (UN-Water, 2017). Another report projects that by 2030, water demand will exceed supply by 50% in most developing regions of the world (Molle and Molinga, 2021).

Nigeria is already facing serious water scarcity problems. This scarcity of water is unfortunately an economic scarcity rather than physical scarcity; water is available in abundance, but has not been

harnessed to meet the needs of the people. The key determinant of water security however is a reliable access to safe water supply and not actual water resource availability. It is estimated that over 65 million people in Nigeria lack access to safe or clean water supply (Majuru, Mokoena, Jagals, and Hunter, 2021). Majority of the people, particularly those living in the rural areas depend on water sources which are unsafe and are consequently susceptible to water borne diseases. These diseases kill over 194,000 people annually, with children below five years being the most affected (Arokoyu & Ukpere, 2014). There are widely expressed fears that water related diseases in the country may double.

There is concern that water resources will come under increased pressure and water could become increasingly scarce. Water withdrawal for agriculture particularly in the drought prone northern part of Nigeria is depleting underground aquifers faster than they can be recharged; urbanization, industrialization and population growth have triggered increased demand for water. Climate change has further exacerbated the already perilous situation as increased temperatures and changing rainfall pattern have either increased variability in river flows (Adelalu, 2012), modified groundwater recharge (Aizebeokhai, 2011) or even caused groundwater pollution (Talabi, Tijani and Aladejana, 2012), thereby increasing the risk of a significant reduction in the volume of water needed to meet the growing demand. If concerted efforts are not put in place to address the water scarcity problem, then a water crisis looms in Nigeria.

What does this portend for the drive to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Nigeria? This paper seeks to address this fundamental question.

Conceptual Clarification

In order to understand the meaning of and context within which some terms are used in this paper, it's important to clarify some concepts. These include: water scarcity, water stress, water security and water crises. These concepts are sometimes misunderstood as mere semantics and mistakenly used interchangeably.

Water Scarcity: This is defined as the lack of sufficient water, or not having access to safe water supplies (Paulson, 2019; Schulte, 2024) and it's measured as a ratio of human water consumption to available water supply in a given area or as the amount of renewable freshwater (not below 1000 m³) that is available for each person each year. UN-Water (2017) defines water scarcity contextually as the point at which the aggregate impact of all users impinges on the supply or quality of water under prevailing institutional arrangements to the extent that the demand by all sectors, including the environment, cannot be satisfied fully. The denominator about these definitions is that a lack of water will lead to scarcity. However, water scarcity may be a social construct (a product of affluence, expectations and customary behaviour) or the consequence of altered supply patterns stemming from climate change (ibid). This highlights the point that water scarcity can sometimes be created by the people, based on what they do or fail to do with water.

Two types of water scarcity exist: physical and economic water scarcity. The former occurs where water supply is limited by natural availability; while the latter occurs where a country or region has abundance water resources but lacks the institutional capacity or economic muscles to harness the water for the benefit of the people. Most countries in sub-Saharan Africa unfortunately suffer from this type of scarcity.

Water Stress: Refers to the ability, or lack thereof, to meet human and ecological demand for water during a certain period (Schulter, 2024). It occurs when less than 1700 cubic meters (448,000 gallons) of fresh water is available per person annually for human use (Global Researcher, 2015). Beyond water availability and accessibility, water stress considers issues such as quality of water, environmental flows and water governance.

Water Security: This concept has been variously defined in the literature. According to Campama (2011), water security is the capacity of a population to access sufficient water to meet all its needs and to limit the destructive aspects of water. To Owuri (2021), water security is more than just having enough water. It seeks to mitigate water-related risks, address conflicts that arise from water. Water Aid (2023) defines water security as the capacity of a population to safeguard sustainable access to adequate quantities of and

acceptable quality water for sustaining livelihoods, human well-being and socio-economic development. The essence is to ensure protection against water-borne pollution and water-related disasters, and for preserving ecosystems in a climate of peace and political stability. It appears this concept is concerned specifically with the safety and security of water supply.

Water Crisis: This is a situation of water scarcity that leads to, or is expected to lead to a dangerous situation affecting a community or the society as a whole in a certain region or country (Naik, 2016). The World Economic Forum (2016) ranks water crisis on the top of ten global risks that threaten economic growth. Water crisis in societies is mostly a crisis of governance and management because this condition occurs mostly in a society where government is corrupt and dysfunctional.

Water Supply situation in Nigeria: Are we heading towards a crisis?

Is Nigeria running out of water? The answer is definitely NO. The country is endowed with enormous water resources, found mostly in the numerous rivers and lakes dissecting the country from the northern part to the southern part. Besides the rivers and lakes, water is also found underground in aquifers. Available estimates put both water sources at a total potential of about 359 billion cubic metres (FMWR, 2011); with surface water accounting for 267.3 billion m³, while groundwater accounts for 92 billion m³. In spite of this massive worth in water, the country still suffers scarcity of water, with access to portable and clean water still very low and uneven. Access to water in Nigeria was 47% in 1990 but rose slightly to 54% in 2010 (The Free Encyclopaedia). In 2013, it was estimated that 58% of the population had access to potable water (Azubike, 2013 cited in Ele, 2013). This shows some level of progress but when compared to the World Health Organization recommended domestic water utilization of 120 litres of water per person/day, it is difficult to say if this is meaningful progress.

Recent reports and physical observation show a much more deplorable situation as people living both in the urban and rural areas have continued to run from pillar to post in search of clean potable water. There is no indication that this situation will change soon. It looks likely that Nigeria is heading towards a water crisis. The fundamental questions are: what are the factors driving Nigeria into a water crisis? How will this situation affect the country's quest to achieving the SDGs?

Factors Driving Nigeria into a Water Crisis

Climate Change: Climate change is one of the major problems the world is facing today. Nigeria is already experiencing the negative effects of climate change and will experience greater changes in future. Climate change scenarios for Nigeria paint a bleak picture of the water sector. Changes in climatic variables particularly rainfall and temperature are likely to result in a reduced availability of freshwater. Available data from meteorological stations across Nigeria indicates high variability and increase in rainfall. This doesn't absolutely imply an increase in water supply. Rather it has triggered more river floods and flash floods experienced across Nigeria in recent times. This has led to the loss of a huge proportion of available surface water, reducing year-round access to water.

Increased temperature will lead to droughts more prolonged than those experienced before. This is also likely to result in a reduced availability of fresh water both on the surface and underground. This situation means a condition of water crisis could be reached much earlier than we anticipate.

Population Increase: Population increase is another force driving the country into a water crisis. According to the Nigeria Health Watch Administration (2016), Nigeria's population was estimated to be 45.2 million in 1960; it rose to 85 million in 1991 then to 140 million in 2006. In 2015, the estimated number of people living in Nigeria was 182.2 million. These figures show an astronomical increase in the population over time.

It appears Nigeria's population is growing faster than development can cater for, faster than the resources to maintain it. One of such resource that is under threat is water. As the population increases, there will be a corresponding increase in demand for water to meet various needs. Water demand already exceeds supply in virtually all parts of Nigeria. It is estimated that Nigeria will need 56 billion litres of potable water supply per day for domestic use (FMWR, 2011) to efficiently serve the projected population of 399

million people by 2050. This appears to be a herculean task to meet giving the current low level of investment and corruption in the water sector.

Infrastructural Decay: Unlike Botswana with perilously few water resources under its control, Nigeria is endowed with abundant water resources. However, the key determinant of water security is reliable access to safe water and not actual water resource availability (Bonsor, MacDonald and Calow, 2021). Sustainable access to water supply can be achieved where there is adequate infrastructure (water plants, a good reticulation network, boreholes etc) to ensure that water gets to the people. In Nigeria water supply infrastructure are either abandoned mid-way, in a state of total disrepair or completely absent. Heavy investments are supposedly made to provide potable water but unfortunately most people still depend on contaminated water sources. For instance, the Benue State government had spent over 5 billion naira between 2007 and 2015, but were unable to deliver water to many homes (Iyorkase, 2006). Where water supply taps are found, many are dry for the better part of the year. Paradoxically, irregular water supply itself hastens the deterioration of water equipment. It is responsible for pipes damages, rust and leakages which further compounds the problem of water supply (Ele, 2013). Concerted efforts and investments must be put into ensuring that we have functional water facilities else the country will run into a crisis similar to what is experienced in the petroleum sector where we have continued to import petroleum products despite the huge oil deposits we control.

Water Pollution: Water is said to be polluted when there is a direct or indirect discharge of pollutants into water bodies without adequate treatment to remove harmful compounds. In Nigeria the contamination of water sources is a major environmental issue that water managers are still struggling to deal with. Water (particularly surface water) is polluted by effluents flushed from big factories; through oil spillage, nitrates and other chemicals from farmlands, household solid waste dumped into water and through mining. Industrial activities and domestic waste have contributed the major source of pollution of our water resources. In the Niger Delta region for instance, it is reported that between 1976 and 2005, Oil put at about 3,121,909.80 barrels was spilled into the environment in about 9,107 incidents (Emuedo, Anoliefo and Emuedo, 2014 citing Department of Petroleum Resources). Apart from oil spillage, gas flaring has also played its part in contaminating fresh water in the region. In Kaduna, effluents flushed from the Kaduna refinery were observed to have contaminated water samples collected at varying points from the river Romi (Lekwot, Adamu and Ayuba, 2012).

Contamination of water attracts a lot of interest because of the importance of water quality on human health. This is because polluted water give rise to water borne diseases which kill hundreds of thousands of people yearly. Water pollution also poses a threat to the available water resources. Though water appears abundant at first sight- almost 70% of the earth's surface is covered with water, less than 1% of this water is readily available for direct human uses (World Wide Fund for Nature, 2017). Water can no longer be taken for granted. Excessive water pollution such as what is currently on-going in Nigeria will affect present and future water supplies with attendant constraints on economic development.

Poor Water Management Practices: Although water is a renewable resource, it's often wasted. For instance, agricultural practices like flood irrigation use fresh water more than necessary. Most of these water is extracted from underground aquifers at unsustainable rate. Annual groundwater withdrawal in Nigeria is estimated at about 2.3 million m³ (FMWR, 2014). Unlike the widely publicised reduction in the size of the Lake Chad, the naked eye can't see when groundwater reserves in aquifers are declining. Water supplies are therefore susceptible to this hidden threat.

In other parts of the world (e.g India, Jordan and United Kingdom), the common practice is to use wastewater for irrigation and for cooling machines in factories. In Nigeria, the perception and use of wastewater is very low. No data is available regarding the volume of wastewater generated and collected. The bulk of wastewater generated is discharged untreated into receiving waters (Omenka, 2010) or indiscriminately on streets and into gutters (Kagu, Badawi and Abba, 2013). Using potable water is regarded to be cheaper than treating and using wastewater. This encourages water wastage.

Water is also seriously undervalued or not valued at all. Most people regard water as a social good rather than an economic good. Hence the resource is not properly managed. Poor water management will put

pressure and threaten available water resources as well as the sustainability of water supply. This brings us to the next issue: what does this portend for Nigeria's quest for achieving the SDGs?

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): A Brief Overview

The 70th session of the United Nations General Assembly in 2015 signed a new global partnership for development tagged- SDGs. The SDGs form a cohesive and integrated package of global aspirations the world commits to achieving in 2030 (Picot and Moss, 2021). Consisting of 17 goals and 169 targets which are universal (designed for both the rich and poor nations), broader, more complex and challenging, the SDGs builds on the strengths and failures of the MDGs. Unlike the MDGs, new areas such as climate change, economic inequality, innovation, sustainable consumption, peace and justice, among other priorities have been included. The goals are interlinked; the key to the success of one will involve tackling issues more commonly associated with another (UNDP, 2017). United Nations member states will be expected to use these goals to frame their agendas and political policies over the next fifteen years in accordance with their own priorities and environmental challenges.

The Centrality of Water in the Realization of the Sustainable Development Goals.

Water is at the core of sustainable development. Water resources, and the range of services they provide, underpin poverty reduction, economic growth and environmental sustainability (UN-Water, 2017). Most often when we reference is made to water, we refer to the SDG 6- which seeks to “ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all”. Water and sanitation (SDG 6) appears to have numerous linkages with the other SDGs. Sindico (2016) classify these linkages as direct and indirect. The linkage is direct when water is directly referred to in the targets of a specific SDG, or indirect when water can be implied from the SDG or its target. This focus of this section is to map and assess the inter-linkages of SDG 6 with other SDGs. The emphasis is more on realising synergies than balancing the trade-offs between water and other SDGs.

Target 6.1: Achieve equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water.

This goal is linked intricately with target 1.4 which advocates equal access to economic resources as well as access to basic services. Water is considered an economic resource and as well as a basic service. Ending poverty (Goal 1) is possible only with sustainable and equitable economic growth, which is not possible without reliable and adequate supply of water (Mugagga and Nabaasa, 2016). Target 6.1 is also linked to 11.4 which aims at providing access to safe and affordable housing and basic services which includes water. Targets 1.5 and 13.1 both mention building and strengthening resilience and adaptive capacity of people particularly the poor by reducing their vulnerability to climate-related events. In the northern part of Nigeria, drought has affected a lot of people. Building resilience to this kind climate-related event is achievable only under conditions of water security, which is directly advocated in all the targets of SDG 6 except in target 6.2 which addresses the issue of sanitation and hygiene.

Target 6.1 is clearly linked with targets 3.1 and 3.2 as without proper access to clean water there will be increased mortality and deaths of new-borns and children. Water-borne diseases can be combated (target 3.3) when people have access to clean water. Target 6.1 also has a link with Goal 4 on ensuring inclusive and quality education for all. Targets 4.1 and 4.2 specifically aim at promoting child development by ensuring access to free, equitable and quality education. This can be achieved when people have access to safe and affordable water. In Nigeria, water supply coverage and access to water is still very low. This places a burden of looking for water on women and children. Many productive hours are lost every day. More importantly performance most children drops because they go to school late and also have limited time to attend to their books after school.

Target 6.1 is also linked to Goal 9, which aims at building resilience infrastructure, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization and fostering innovation. Developing “quality, sustainable, reliable and resilient infrastructure” (Target 9.1), will include investments in water infrastructure. This will definitely help to support economic growth and human well-being.

Target 6.2: Achieve access to equitable sanitation and hygiene.

This target is also linked to targets 3.1 and 3.2 as without reasonable access to sanitation and hygiene reducing mortality and deaths of new-borns and children will be a difficult task. This problem will be further compounded if target 6.1 (above) is not implemented.

Target 6.3: Improving water quality by reducing pollution.

This target is linked to target 3.3 on “combating water-borne diseases and other communicable diseases. It is easy to prevent water-borne diseases when people access water that is free from pollution. In addition, when target 3.3 is implemented, target 3.9 which is to substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from water pollution and contamination, which is listed along with soil and air pollution can be achieved. This highlights how one SDG cannot be met without the other. Ending hunger and ensuring access to safe, nutritious and sufficient food referred to in target 2.1 can be achieved if target 6.3 is implemented. Targets 6.3 and 12.4- which has a mandate to significantly reduce the release of chemicals waste into water (among other things) in order to minimise their adverse impacts on human health and environment-are intricately linked. Both targets seek to address water pollution and its effects. If implemented, both targets will help in achieving targets 14.1(to prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution) and 14.2 (substantially manage and protect marine and coastal ecosystems to avoid significant adverse impacts).

Target 6.4: Increase water-use efficiency to address water scarcity problems.

Water is also linked to Goal 2. Water of appropriate quantity (target 6.4) is essential for ensuring sustainable food production systems (target 2.4). It is essential for food processing, transformation and preparation, as typified in a garri production process. In addition, to ensure that agricultural productivity and income of farmers is doubled (target 2.3), it would be necessary to ensure that our water resources are sustainably managed (target 6.4) using options like rainwater harvesting and wastewater recycling improve water supply to boost agriculture. Ending hunger and ensuring access to safe, nutritious and sufficient food (target 2.4) can only be when targets 6.3 and 6.4 are achieved.

Water is critical for energy generation (Goal 7) and energy is necessary for the extraction of safe drinking water (Le Blanc, 2015). Increasing water-use efficiency (target 6.4) is key to promoting and ensuring universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy (target 7.1). This is largely because water is used in energy extraction and processing. Target 7.2 calls for an increase in the share of “renewable energy.” This should include hydropower which is widely regarded as a source of sustainable energy. Hydropower accounts for 17.8% of the total energy consumed in Africa (UNIDO, 2019). Increasing hydropower generation will mean building or upgrading infrastructure such as large scale dams (target 9.4). This in turn will adversely affect the environment.

Improving global resource efficiency in consumption and production, and decoupling economic growth from environmental degradation (target 8.4) will require employing efficient use of water (target 6.4) to avert water scarcity. A close look at the SDGs will show that achieving target 8.4 will also require implementing target 12.1, which aims at ensuring sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources which includes water. Successfully implementing target 8.1 (sustain per capita economic growth) will depend generally on SDG 6 expect target 6.2 on sanitation and hygiene. The other targets aim at achieving water security which is a necessary condition for sustainable economic growth (UN DESA, 2015).

Target 6.5: Implement integrated water resource management (IWRM) at all levels, including through trans-boundary cooperation.

This target is linked to and crucial for the achievement of target 7.1 which aims at ensuring universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy by 2030. Integrated water resource management promotes the coordinated development and management of water through building water infrastructure like dams that are used for hydropower generation and subsequent distribution to consumers. The part on IWRM also calls for participation of women, which target 5.5 addresses by ensuring that there is women’s full and effective participation as well as equal opportunities for leadership at all levels.

Ensuring responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels (target 16.7) also resonates with the concept of IWRM.

The second part of target 6.5 on trans-boundary cooperation relates with Goal 10, as this ensures that there is a 'Reduction of inequality within and among countries' through equitable distribution of shared water resources. Trans-boundary cooperation will reduce the growing pressure on water resources noticed in many river basins. This will consequently help to significantly reduce water conflicts/violence and deaths which is the mandate of target 16.1. Another benefit of trans-boundary cooperation on water is that it will significantly increase the exports of developing countries so as to double the share of global exports.

Target 6.6: Protect and restore water related ecosystems: mountains, lakes, rivers, lakes

This target is closely linked with Goal 15 which has the mandate to "Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss." Specifically, target 6.6 is directly linked with target 15.1. Both targets seek to protect, restore and conserve all water-related ecosystems. This is the main focus of sustainable development – to ensure that resources are used in a manner that does not jeopardize future use. Protecting and restoring water-related ecosystems involves adapting good water management practices which can help to combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil (target 15.3).

Target 6.6 is equally linked with target 7.2 though a trade-off is involved. Increasing substantially the share of renewable energy (including hydropower) in the global mix (target 7.2), will put pressure on water resources. This will in a way impede the efforts aimed at achieving target 6.6 especially where there are many uses or users competing for the water. Trans-boundary cooperation (target 6.5) is recommended as a way of balancing this type of trade-off.

Target 6a: Expand international cooperation and capacity-building support to developing countries in water and sanitation activities and programs.

This target is linked with Goal 16 which is a mandate on promoting peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development in addition to providing access to justice for all. Expanding international cooperation especially in river basins where water is shared by many countries can significantly reduce all forms of violence (including water wars) and deaths (target 16.1). Among all renewable resources, water has the greatest potential for stimulating international wars, especially where the users downstream of a river are seriously affected (Gleditseh, Furlong, Hegre, Lacina and Owen, 2016). Target 6a re-echo the need to implement target 6.5.

Target 6b: Support and strengthen the participation of local communities in improving water and sanitation management.

This target is linked with Goal 5 which places emphasis on achieving gender equality and girls and women empowerment. To "support and strengthen the participation of local communities," would mean including women in decision making about water and sanitation management (particularly in the area of managing water and sanitation infrastructure) in their communities. This way, discrimination against women will be eliminated (target 5.1). Consequently, women will be given equal rights, access to ownership and control over economic resources (including water) as highlighted in target 5a.

CONCLUSION

Water is a very important resource and it's central to the realization of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as demonstrated by the review of the synergies between water and the other SDGs. The major challenge for African countries including Nigeria is how to secure access to water needed to meet the needs of the people. Addressing this challenge should be a top priority for the government in order to avert a water crisis. This because a water crisis in Nigeria will trigger many socio-economic problems -- food insecurity, increased vulnerability to climate-related events, water conflicts, energy and industrial production difficulties- all of which hinder sustainable economic growth. It is therefore in the interest of Government to work towards achieving water security. Achieving the dedicated SDG on water and sanitation therefore becomes very key. However, achieving all the Sustainable Development Goals will

requires more than just meeting the goal on water. The Government will need to adopt the systems approach; a situation that provides a platform where the synergies between water and the other SDGs are duly exploited.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this paper, the following recommendations are made:

- (i) A commission of inter-related Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) be created by Government to work together towards achieving the SDGs in Nigeria.
- (ii) Budgetary allocations towards water resource development should be increased so as to increase access to water among people. This is because access to water will drive development in the other sectors of the economy.
- (iii) The Nigerian Government should spear-head the campaign for increased data and information sharing on hydrological and meteorological activities among fellow countries that share trans-boundary waters. This will help boost water supply.

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